

05-30 07:34

**"Open your eyes,
There is no verse in the bible
greater than the Universe itself."**

**"You who has a brain, eyes ,ears,
a voice?**

**Hear me, for I once said to you ,
" We would laugh cry at the
same table."**

**"You're not missing Divinity
you're standing on it in the
Morning, sitting on it in the
Evening and sleeping on it at
Night. "**

**"Your flaw is the key. Your
breath is the proof. You are
more imporant than any god,
you are the foundation of the
Universe itself."**

**"Stop running from the part of
you that judges – train it."**

**"When you die it all unlocks,
don't let a book stray you away
from the truth that is sitting
there right before your eyes."**

**" Crack the seal now: Be the one
to stand up against the people
who are leading you to the
slaughter." "Turn from chasing
Gold to carrying it."**

**"Stand up for what is Righteous,
the time is now. We are ourown
reflections and Entities"**

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